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Title: Real-time monitoring of organic apple (var. Gala) during hot-air drying using near-infrared spectroscopy

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Abstract: Dried apple (*Malus domestica* B.) shows a growing trend to its worldwide consumption as raw material to produce organic snacks, integral breakfast foods, chips, etc. Apple is often dried by conventional methods (e.g. hot-air drying, freeze-drying, etc.), which are usually uncontrolled and then prone to product quality deterioration. Thus, there is a need for the development of new drying systems able to guarantee high-value end products. In this study, the feasibility of NIR spectroscopy as smart drying technology to non-destructively detect and monitor physicochemical changes in organic apples wedges during 8-h hot-air drying at 60°C has been investigated. Moreover, the impact of microwave heating pre-treatment (at 850W for 45 sec) as enzyme inactivators on model performances was also evaluated. Partial least squares (PLS) regression models were successfully developed to monitor changes in water activity ($R^2 = 0.97 \div 0.98$), moisture content ($R^2 = 0.97 \div 0.98$), SSC ($R^2 = 0.96 \div 0.97$) and chroma ($R^2 = 0.77 \div 0.86$) during drying. Classification analysis was performed for the development of discriminant models able to recognise dehydration phases of apple wedges on the basis of their spectral profile. The classification models were computed using K-means and Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) algorithms in sequence. The performance of each PLS-DA model was defined based on its accuracy, sensitivity and specificity rates. All of the selected models provided a very-good (>0.90) or excellent (>0.95) sensitivity and specificity rates for the predefined drying phases. Feature selection procedures allowed to obtain both regression and classification models with performances very similar to models computed from the full spectrum. Results suggest that effect of microwave heating on both water loss and microstructure of apple tissue was pronounced, mainly affecting the features selection procedure in terms of number of features and selected wavelengths.

HIGHLIGHTS

- NIR spectroscopy is a feasible method to control and monitor apple drying
- PLS allows reliable measurement of physicochemical parameters during drying
- PLS-DA allows reliable detection of drying phases of apple wedges
- Microwave treatment affects feature selection for both PLS and PLS-DA models

1 **Real-time monitoring of organic apple (var. *Gala*) during hot-air drying**
2 **using near-infrared spectroscopy**

3
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12
13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Dried apple (*Malus domestica* B.) shows a growing trend to its worldwide consumption as raw
15 material to produce organic snacks, integral breakfast foods, chips, etc. Apple is often dried by
16 conventional methods (e.g. hot-air drying, freeze-drying, etc.), which are usually uncontrolled and
17 then prone to product quality deterioration. Thus, there is a need for the development of new drying
18 systems able to guarantee high-value end products. In this study, the feasibility of NIR spectroscopy
19 as smart drying technology to non-destructively detect and monitor physicochemical changes in
20 organic apples wedges during 8-h hot-air drying at 60°C has been investigated. Moreover, the
21 impact of microwave heating pre-treatment (at 850W for 45 sec) as enzyme inactivators on model
22 performances was also evaluated. Partial least squares (PLS) regression models were successfully
23 developed to monitor changes in water activity ($R^2 = 0.97 \div 0.98$), moisture content ($R^2 =$
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27 computed using K-means and Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) algorithms in
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30 sensitivity and specificity rates for the predefined drying phases. Feature selection procedures
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37 feature selection

38

39 **1.0 INTRODUCTION**

40 Globalization of market entails the availability of horticultural products regardless of their
41 harvest date, pursued through innovation in products and processes to obtain fruit and vegetables
42 with improved shelf-life, organoleptic quality, nutritional value, safety and healthiness during the
43 whole agrofood chain. Consequently, market value of perishable commodity mainly depends on the
44 preservation method used to guarantee food stability and thus to delay physicochemical,
45 biochemical and microbiological spoilage (Aghbashlo et al., 2015). In fact, the preservation method
46 directly affects processing, storage, transportation and distribution costs.

47 Among postharvest operations, drying is one of the oldest, typical, effective and viable
48 preservation processes throughout the world. It consists of three main interlinked steps that can be
49 summarized as: (1) product formulation or treatment selection, (2) dehydration process and (3)
50 quality and properties assessment (Aghbashlo et al., 2015). Drying prevents food spoilage and
51 decay through moisture removal due to simultaneous heat and mass transfer from foods, which may
52 be stored for long periods with minimal deterioration occurring (Nadian et al., 2015). In absence of

53 sufficient water, microorganisms grow slowly and many of the moisture-mediated reactions, which
54 are responsible for undesirable chemical changes, do not function properly (Mayor and Sereno,
55 2004; Demirhan and Özbek, 2009). Despite this, drying is not only used to significantly extend
56 shelf-life and nutritional quality of fruit, vegetables, spices and herbs as well as meat and fish, but
57 also to substantially minimize storage and shipping costs (Grabowski et al., 2003). In fact, drying is
58 particularly effective in enabling storability of food at room temperature and simplifying product
59 handling by reducing weight and packaging volume (Liu et al., 2016). Drying technology may vary
60 from simple methods (e.g. sun drying) to relatively advanced techniques (e.g. instant controlled
61 pressure drop drying); nevertheless, modern technology schemes are not always paired with
62 good/excellent quality and high commodity value (Chong et al., 2014; Nadian et al., 2015). In fact,
63 drying is a relatively complex, dynamic, unsteady and nonlinear process that may suffer from
64 properties of wet material, scale of production and compliance with regulations, as well as operating
65 and environmental conditions (Aghbashlo et al., 2015). They may be responsible for quality
66 degradation and result in reduction of consumer acceptance through undesirable changes in colour,
67 texture, size and shape as well as organoleptic, nutritional and functional properties (Brosnan and
68 Sun, 2004; Vega-Gálvez et al., 2012). Last but not least, drying is one of the most energy-intensive
69 processes in food industry (Akpınar et al., 2003); in fact, it adversely effects climate change as most
70 dryers use fossil fuels (Mujumdar, 2012). Consequently, with the aim of circumventing the
71 aforementioned issues, new drying technologies must be designed around the quality attributes of
72 the raw material to ensure valuable products at the highest drying rate and the lowest carbon
73 footprint, which means minimal/optimal energy demand and negligible environmental impact
74 (Mujumdar, 2012; Su et al., 2015). Among emerging drying technologies, smart drying is one of the
75 newest and most promising techniques. It has potential to guarantee high-value end products, while
76 enhancing drying efficiency, by implementing innovative and reliable sensors, resources, tools and
77 practices. Moreover, smart drying can be cost-effective in both real-time monitoring of foodstuffs
78 quality and dynamic controlling of operating conditions along the whole drying process. Smart

79 drying is a multi- and inter-disciplinary sector and its recent developments embrace the following
80 R&D areas: artificial intelligence (Aghbashlo et al., 2015), biomimetic (Ghasemi-Varnamkhasti et
81 al., 2010), computer vision (Brosnan and Sun, 2004), microwave/dielectric spectroscopy (Jha et al.,
82 2011), visible (Vis) and near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy (Nicolai et al., 2007), hyper-
83 /multispectral imaging (ElMasry and Sun, 2010), magnetic resonance imaging (Clarka et al., 1997;
84 Su et al., 2014), ultrasound imaging (Awad et al., 2012), electrostatic sensing (Chen et al., 2013)
85 and control system for the drying environment.

86 Among commercial fruits, apple shows a growing trend to its worldwide consumption
87 (Rodríguez et al., 2014), where dried apple plays a major role in food industry as raw material for
88 the production of snacks, integral breakfast foods, chips, etc., which have become popular in the
89 diet of modern consumers (Vega-Gálvez et al., 2012; Yi et al., 2015) in parallel with the human
90 consumption of organic products (Sacilik and Elicin, 2006). Despite apple tissue exhibits extensive
91 and not homogeneous discoloration during drying (Fernández et al., 2005), it is nowadays often
92 dried by conventional methods (e.g. hot-air drying, freeze-drying, etc.) which, however, are usually
93 uncontrolled and then prone to product quality deterioration as well as the fact of being affected by
94 a number of drawbacks, such as very long drying time and, of course, high energy demand (Chong
95 et al., 2014; Nadian et al., 2015). Thus, treatment selection before apple drying is a mandatory (but
96 not sufficient) step to obtain a high-value end product. However, because not all conventional
97 drying treatments are allowed by the European Organic Regulation on production and labelling of
98 organic products (i.e. EC No. 834/2007 and EC No. 889/2008), drying of organic apples should be
99 carefully optimized to obtain comparable results to conventional methods.

100 Therefore, the main objective of the proposed study was to investigate the feasibility of
101 near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy as smart drying technology to proactively and non-destructively
102 detect and monitor quality change in organic apple wedges during hot-air drying. Based on authors'
103 best knowledge, apple drying has been widely addressed in literature; nevertheless, little insight is
104 available on smart drying of apples, while knowledge of its potential use in the organic sector is

105 totally lacking. NIR spectroscopy was investigated as proved on-/in-line tool with high sensitivity
106 to changes in moisture content, particle size and chemical state of food (Ozaki et al., 2006).

107 **2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

108 *2.1 Sample preparation*

109 Organic apples (*Malus domestica* B. var. Gala) were purchased from a local organic trader
110 (Biobox srl, Viterbo, Italy) and immediately stored at 4 ± 1 °C until processing. Fruit sampling was
111 performed by selecting sound apples, with uniform size and same ripening stage. Fruits were
112 tempered to room temperature 15 h before starting the experimental activities.

113 Apple wedges, without core and peel, were prepared by washing and cutting fruit into discs
114 (5-mm thick) and subsequently dividing each disc into quarters using a cork borer and a sharp
115 ceramic knife. Samples were visually evaluated for quality assessment and only apple wedges free
116 from decay and/or blemish were used in the experimentation to perform (1) hot-water blanching and
117 microwave heating treatments and (2) hot-air drying tests.

118 About 100 g of apple wedges were used for both hot-water and microwave treatment
119 experiments, while 270 apple wedges were randomly arranged into 9 batches of 30 samples each for
120 the use in drying experiment. Fruit wedges were subjected to 8-h hot-air drying and batch sampling
121 was performed at 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 h drying. Each batch was subjected to both NIR spectral
122 data acquisition and determination of CIELab color, moisture content, water activity (a_w) and
123 soluble solids content.

124 *2.2 Treatment before hot-air dehydration*

125 *2.2.1 Hot-water blanching*

126 Hot-water blanching consisted of dipping apple wedges in hot-water with a temperature
127 controlled water bath (Astor 800D, Astori Tecnica, Brescia, Italy). As a control, apple wedges were
128 dipped in distilled water at room temperature. The experimental plan is reported in Table 1. Treated
129 samples were immediately cooled for 3 min in ice-water, and the residual POD enzymatic activity
130 was evaluated.

131 2.2.2 *Microwave heating*

132 A turntable domestic microwave oven (MT243, Whirlpool Co., Michigan, United States)
133 with a continuous output-power (2450 MHz, 1000 W) was used to treat apple wedges. An
134 experimental design based on a factorial design was applied (Table 1). Powers and times of
135 treatment were chosen by taking into consideration the results of preliminary experiments aimed at
136 identifying proper process conditions to allow apple wedges to be uniformly treated. After
137 treatment, apple wedges were removed from the microwave oven and immediately dipped in ice-
138 water for 3 min to accelerate cooling. Residual POD activity was then evaluated.

139 2.3 *Peroxidase activity*

140 2.3.1 *Enzyme purification*

141 Enzyme purification was carried out on the basis of the method of Massantini et al. (2009)
142 with some modifications. Apple wedges were collected after each blanching treatment, frozen with
143 liquid nitrogen and then immediately grinded into frozen powder by an analytic mill (IKA A11
144 basic; IKA Labortechnik, Staufen, Germany). Three grams of apple powder were homogenized
145 with 15 mL of chilled phosphate buffer solution (PBS, 0.1 mol L⁻¹, pH 6.5) containing 3% (w/v) of
146 polyvinylpolypyrrolidone. The mixture was centrifuged at 13,800 × g for 20 min at 4 °C and the
147 supernatant was used in the experimentation.

148 2.3.2 *Enzyme activity measurement*

149 Peroxidase (POD) activity was measured by following the method of Moschetti et al. (2012)
150 with slight modifications. The assay was performed using an UV-Vis scanning spectrophotometer
151 (Lambda 25; PerkinElmer, Massachusetts, United States). Changes in the absorbance at 460 nm
152 were monitored for 3 min upon oxidation of the substrates catalysed by the enzyme. Guaiacol
153 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, United States) was used as substrate. The final reaction
154 mixture contained 1 mL of crude enzyme, 1 mL of PBS (0.1 mol L⁻¹, pH 6.5), 1 mL of guaiacol
155 (0.25% v/v) and 0.01 mL of hydrogen peroxide (0.75% v/v). One unit of enzyme activity (1 UEA)

156 was defined as an increase in absorbance of 0.001 min^{-1} . Enzyme activity was measured in
157 triplicate.

158 2.3.3 Enzyme thermal inactivation

159 The rate constant for first-order inactivation (k) was computed from the slope of the linear
160 regression of the natural log of residual activity versus time of thermal treatment, according to Eq. 1

$$161 \quad (1) \quad \ln(E_t / E_0) = -kt$$

162 where E_0 is the initial enzyme activity (UEA), E_t is the activity after heating for time t
163 (UEA), t is the time of heating (min) and k is the inactivation rate constant (min^{-1}). The coefficient
164 of determination (R^2) of each regression line was also computed.

165 A POD inactivation of 90% was fixed as threshold in order to consider the produce stable
166 for the industrial requirements (Benlloch-Tinoco et al., 2013). Consequently, inactivation time was
167 computed as *D-value* (or decimal reduction time) as treatment time required to reduce the enzyme
168 activity to at least 0.1 (i.e. 10% of its original value), according to Eq. 2.

$$169 \quad (2) \quad E_t / E_0 = E_0 (1/2)^{t/t_{1/2}}$$

170 2.4 Hot-air dehydration process

171 The hot-air drying experiment was performed in a 5-tray dryer (Biosec, Tauro Essicatori srl,
172 Vicenza, Italy). The dryer consisted in a temperature controller and a centrifugal fan that was used
173 to blow air into the heating unit through a 15-cm duct. The air flow was parallel to the drying
174 surface of the apple wedge. The dehydration process was conducted at 60°C for 8 h on the basis of
175 screening results obtained from tests conducted in the range from 40 to 60°C . Drying tests at
176 temperatures lower than 60°C were discarded due samples developing browning within the first 2
177 hours of dehydration.

178 2.5 Near infrared spectroscopy

179 2.5.1 Spectral acquisition

180 Diffuse reflectance spectra were acquired using a Luminar 5030 Acousto-Optic Tunable
181 Filter-Near Infrared (AOTF-NIR) Miniature ‘Hand-held’ Analyzer coupled with the bundled
182 ‘SNAP! 2.04’ software (Brimrose Corp., Baltimore, USA). The instrument was equipped with a
183 reflectance post-dispersive optical configuration, a pre-aligned dual beam lamp assembly and an
184 indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs) array (range 1100-2300 nm, 2-nm resolution) with an integrating
185 time of 60 msec. The reference spectrum was automatically measured by the instrument following
186 the method used by Moschetti et al. (2013a). Each sample was measured in duplicate on two opposite
187 sides of each apple wedge (i.e. 4 spectra per sample). Reflectance spectra were converted to
188 absorbance ($A = \log R^{-1}$) and the average spectrum was used for further computations.

189 2.5.2 Spectral pre-treatments

190 Each apple wedge was modelled as a ‘data vector’, where the spectral absorbance values
191 (otherwise called features) were vector components. Chemometric analysis was performed
192 following spectral pre-treatments including Standard Normal Variate (SNV), Multiplicative Scatter
193 Correction (MSC), and Savitzky-Golay first and second derivatives ($D1f$ and $D2f$, respectively)
194 with a second or third order polynomial fitted over a window of five (S5), seven (S7), nine (S9) or
195 eleven (S11) features (Savitzky and Golay, 1964; Boysworth and Booksh, 2008). For each dataset,
196 Mean Centering (MC) was also tested as spectral pre-treatment. Every possible combination of pre-
197 processing was also tested and only best results, in terms of model performances, were retained.

198 2.5.3 Chemometrics

199 2.5.3.1 Prediction of chemical and physicochemical changes (regression models development)

200 Regression models were computed using the partial least squares (PLS) regression through
201 the SIMPLS algorithm (de Jong, 1993). PLS is a regression technique used to find some linear
202 combinations of the original independent variables. By using these linear combinations alone, PLS
203 allowing the discarding of irrelevant and unstable information, solving collinearity problem and,
204 finally, obtaining a more stable regression equation. In addition, the Interval PLS (iPLS) algorithm
205 was also used to select a subset of wavelengths which could describe superior prediction compared

206 to PLS models based on all features dataset (Xing et al., 2008). The iPLS algorithm was configured
207 in stepwise forward mode for the selection of a maximum of 10 wavelengths.

208 As PLS and iPLS regressions perform a dimensionality reduction, it is essential to test each
209 model and select the correct number of latent variables to find the optimal trade-off between under-
210 fitting and over-fitting. Thus, the samples were randomly split as follows: 75% and 25% of the
211 samples were assigned to the calibration set (C) and the prediction set (P), respectively. Every PLS
212 and iPLS model was optimized by computing a venetian blinds cross-validation with 10 data splits.
213 This cross-validation method was preferred because it is simple and easy to implement, relatively
214 fast, generally safe and capable of providing a better representation when the dataset contains many
215 samples, as is the case here (Naes et al., 2004; Wise, 2009). Root Mean Squared Error for
216 calibration, cross-validation and prediction calculations (RMSEC, RMSECV and RMSEP,
217 respectively) were employed to evaluate each regression model with the purpose of selecting the
218 optimal number of latent variables and thus circumvent unrealistic results (Moscetti et al., 2015).
219 Model performances were also evaluated in terms of BIAS and coefficient of determination (R^2).

220 PLS and iPLS models were both computed to predict changes in chemical and
221 physicochemical attributes during 8-h dehydration process.

222 2.5.3.2 Prediction of the drying phases (classification models development)

223 Classification models were developed using K-means and Partial Least Squares
224 Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) algorithms in sequence (Fig. 1). As initial step, K-means was
225 employed to determine the number of drying phases (i.e. classes) and to label each sample as
226 belonging to a specific class on the basis of the observed changes in moisture content, water
227 activity, CIELab color and soluble solids content. K-means is a partitional clustering method
228 belonging to the group of the unsupervised hierarchical cluster analyses. The selection of the most
229 appropriate cluster solution was performed by computing both actual and random sum of squared
230 errors (SSE) for a maximum of 9 clusters (i.e. 9 times of dehydration). Random SSEs were
231 computed from 300 randomized versions of the original dataset. To determine the optimal cluster

232 level, the scree plots of both (1) the actual SSE versus the cluster solutions and (2) the difference
233 between the actual and random SSEs against the cluster solutions, were investigated. The best
234 cluster level was chosen as solution at which the plot of the actual SSE versus clusters produced an
235 “elbow” and the actual SSE differed the most from the average of the random SSEs.

236 As a final step, the identified class membership was used as response variable (Y) for the
237 development of PLS-DA models in which the predictor variables (X) were spectral profiles. Thus,
238 PLS-DA was used to assign each apple wedge to a specific dehydration phase on the basis of its
239 spectral profile. Moreover, the Interval PLS-DA (iPLS-DA) algorithm was used to identify and test
240 a maximum of 10 features. As in PLS regression model, the RMSE analysis was performed to
241 select the optimal number of latent variables also for both PLS-DA and iPLS-DA classification
242 models (Goodarzi et al., 2013). The classification performance of each PLS-DA and iPLS-DA
243 model was determined in terms of sensitivity (Eq. 3), selectivity (Eq. 4) and accuracy (Eq. 5) rates
244 (Dejaegher et al., 2011). In detail, accuracy rate was used to mainly select models in terms of
245 predictivity, while sensitivity and specificity rates were jointly employed to perform a model sub-
246 selection in terms of robustness (i.e. the capability of the model to resist to small changes in test
247 conditions).

$$248 \quad (3) \quad \textit{Sensitivity rate} = \frac{\textit{True Positives}}{\textit{True Positives} + \textit{False Negatives}}$$

$$249 \quad (4) \quad \textit{Selectivity rate} = \frac{\textit{True Negatives}}{\textit{False Positives} + \textit{True Negatives}}$$

$$250 \quad (5) \quad \textit{Accuracy rate} = \frac{\textit{True Positives} + \textit{True Negatives}}{\textit{Total Positives} + \textit{Total Negatives}}$$

251 Similarly to what already described for the development of regression models, the dataset was
252 randomly split in calibration and prediction sets (75% and 25% of samples, respectively) and every
253 PLS-DA model was optimized by computing a venetian blinds cross-validation with 10 data splits.

254 *2.6 Chemical and physicochemical attributes*

255 Both chemical and physicochemical attributes were measured immediately after the NIR
256 spectral acquisitions.

257 Colour of apple wedge was measured with a spectrophotometer (CM-2600d, Konica
258 Minolta, Osaka, Japan). The mode used for acquiring data was CIE Standard Illuminant D65
259 (Daylight), Observer 10° and 6-mm diameter of measurement aperture. Four replications were
260 performed for each sample by performing two colour measurements on two opposite sides of each
261 apple wedge. The results were expressed according to the CIELab colour space and thus in terms of
262 lightness (L^*), redness (a^*), yellowness (b^*), hue angle (h) and chroma (C^*) (Moscetti et al.,
263 2013a).

264 Moisture content was measured following the official method ‘Moisture in Dried Fruits’ -
265 AOAC 934.06 and was expressed as a percentage by mass (grams per 100 grams) (Horwitz, 2005).

266 Water activity (a_w) was determined with an Aqua Lab (3TE, Decagon Devices Inc.,
267 Washington, USA).

268 Soluble solids content (SSC) was measured with a digital refractometer mod. WM-7 (Atago,
269 Tokyo, Japan) by following the method of Lavelli and Kerr (2012) with slight modifications. The
270 vortexed and centrifuged extract of 350 mg of freeze-dried sample with 10 mL of distilled water
271 was measured. Results were then converted on a fresh weight basis and expressed as °Brix (grams
272 of sucrose per 100 g of fresh product).

273

274 *2.7 Statistical analysis and data mining*

275 One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate statistical differences
276 among the drying times. The Tukey’s pairwise comparison method was performed, and the
277 Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) was calculated for an appropriate level of interaction ($P \leq$
278 0.05) (Montgomery, 2001). Results were reported as the mean and standard error of the mean.
279 Before statistical analysis, results relative to moisture content were subjected to angular

280 transformation (i.e. $y = \arcsine [x]^{1/2}$) to homogenize the variance (Bartlett's test) (Gomez and
281 Gomez, 1984). The data reported in the tables and figures were back transformed.

282 Data handling and ANOVA were both performed using R v3.2.4 software in combination
283 with 'agricolae' v1.2-3 R-package (CRAN, 2016). Chemometrics was performed using Matlab
284 software R2015a coupled with PLS_Toolbox software v8.1 (Eigenvector Research Inc., WA, USA).

285

286 3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

287 In the present research work, the apple drying process was monitored using NIR
288 spectroscopy. NIR-based regression and classification models were computed and the impact of
289 thermal treatments as enzyme inactivators on model performances was also investigated.

290

291 3.1 Thermal treatment selection

292 The effect of thermal treatments on apple wedges was evaluated for both hot-water
293 blanching and microwave heating treatments at pre-established range of temperature and power,
294 respectively (Table 1). To monitor the thermal treatment, peroxidase was used as indicator enzyme
295 due to its higher thermal stability and easiness in being assayed. In fact, the POD inactivation gives
296 reasonable assumption that other quality-deteriorative enzymes (e.g. pectinmethylesterase,
297 polyphenol oxidase, etc.) are also inactivated.

298 Inactivation kinetics were determined through semi-log plot of residual POD activity versus
299 time. Results showed excellent linear fits ($R^2 = 0.93\div 0.99$) at all temperatures/powers studied,
300 consistent with inactivation occurring by first-order kinetics (Fig. 2). Although all treatments
301 reached the inactivation threshold (decimal reduction, 90%), considerably faster reductions in POD
302 activity were only achieved with microwave heating (Fig. 2b). In fact, hot-water blanching was less
303 effective, showing slowest inactivation rate constants (k) (0.17, 0.46 and 0.79 min^{-1} at 80, 90 and
304 95°C, respectively) in comparison with microwave heating (1.08, 1.81 and 3.03 min^{-1} at 350, 650
305 and 850 W, respectively). Moreover, microwave treatment led to better colour retention in apple
306 wedges than hot-water blanching (data not shown). Although the mechanism is still unclear and
307 several controversial opinions must be faced (Awuah et al., 2007), similar results were reported by
308 several authors (Awuah et al., 2007; Matsui et al., 2008; Zheng and Lu, 2011; Latorre et al., 2012;
309 Rattanadecho and Makul, 2016). It seems that microwave irradiation may be more effective and
310 faster for facing enzyme inactivation when compared with conventional methods, because of
311 concurrent thermal (i.e. heat denaturation of protein) and non-thermal (i.e. microwaves interaction

312 with polar and/or charged moieties of protein) effects of microwaves (Olsen et al., 1966; Kermasha
313 et al., 1993; Matsui et al., 2008; Rattanadecho and Makul, 2016).

314 Finally, the lowest decimal reduction time (D) among treatments was achieved by using
315 microwave at 850 W for 0.77 min (~ 46.2 sec) of irradiation. Thus, considering that the evaluation
316 of the effects of thermal treatment on nutritional value of product was not part of the present study,
317 microwave heating at 850 W for 45 sec was selected as the most adequate treatment to obtain
318 colour-stable apple wedges to use further in the experimentation.

319

320 *3.2 Spectral data overview*

321 Fig. 3 depicts the resulting mean relative absorbance spectra obtained from the AOTF-NIR
322 spectrophotometer in the 1100-2300-nm spectral range. Fig. 3a and 3b provide information about
323 spectral differences between treatments (i.e. control and microwave heating treatments,
324 respectively) and among drying times. Specifically, changes in the spectral profiles during the
325 drying process were evident to the naked eye for the control treatment only. In fact, it should be
326 noted that drying time heavily affected the spectral characteristics in the water absorption bands
327 (1450 and 1940 nm) (Saeys et al., 2008) and, more generally, in the higher wavelength region
328 (1900-2300 nm), which is notably associated with carbohydrates, starch and proteins (Ambrose et
329 al., 2016). On the other hand, microwave-heated samples apparently showed less changes in
330 spectral shape during the drying process and less pronounced shoulders on either side of the two
331 principal water absorption bands (1450 and 1940 nm). Results allow to speculate that those
332 differences in spectral profile should be mainly due to both water loss and changes in forward
333 scattering and backscattering by flesh tissue as consequence of the microwave heating treatment.

334

335 *3.3 Chemical and physicochemical changes*

336 Table 2 summarizes changes in chemical and physicochemical parameters on treated (i.e.
337 microwave heated) and untreated (i.e. control) apple wedges subjected to 8-h drying. ANOVA

338 indicates a significant effect of drying time on each quality parameter. Moisture content and water
339 activity gradually decreased during drying time, while SSC increased due to decline in water
340 content. Results were perfectly in agreement with those of other authors (Romano et al., 2011;
341 Dénes et al., 2012). However, different drying behaviours between treatments were noted. In fact,
342 microwave-treated samples showed a faster decrease in water activity during drying and a higher
343 experimental variability for SSC, probably due to the higher heterogeneity of the raw material. The
344 data also pointed that colour of treated apple wedges was totally different from the untreated one.
345 Microwave heating entailed less colour changes during drying and it was responsible for lower
346 initial (0-h drying) and final (8-h drying) CIELab values of lightness (L^*), redness (a^*) and
347 yellowness (b^*) of product. Although microwave heating better retained the colour due to reduction
348 in enzymatic browning, colour changes during drying showed a similar trend between treatments,
349 probably due to Maillard reaction occurrence. In general, the variation in L^* value was unclear and
350 practically independent of thermal treatment, similarly to the results obtained by Krokida et al.
351 (1998, 2001); while drying time was found to increase redness (a^*), yellowness (b^*) and chroma
352 (C^*) and to decrease hue-angle (h).

353 The chemical and physicochemical features of 270 apple wedges per treatment were
354 clustered using the K-means algorithm. A cluster analysis was performed in each treatment group.
355 On the basis of the scree plots obtained for the difference between the actual and random SSEs
356 against the cluster solutions (data not shown), the optimal cluster level was identified as three and
357 thus samples were split into three main classes, each characterized by a specific drying period (also
358 named ‘Drying phase I’, ‘Drying phase II’ and ‘Drying phase III’) (Table 2). Results showed that
359 the duration of drying phases slightly differed between treatments. In fact, the control treatment
360 showed a shorter ‘Drying phase II’ (i.e. from 3 to 4 hours of drying) in comparison with the
361 microwave heating treatment (i.e. from 3 to 5 hours of drying).

362 Data from the analysis of quality parameters and labels from the K-means analysis were
363 both used as Y-vector for the development of regression and classification models, respectively.

364

365

366 3.3 Regression models

367 The complete calibration and prediction performances of the regression models are
368 summarized in Table 3. PLS regression models with good or excellent predictability were obtained
369 to monitor changes in a_w (Fig. 3a), moisture content (Fig. 3b), chroma (Fig. 3c) and SSC (Fig. 3d)
370 of apples wedges during drying, regardless both thermal treatment and number of features used in
371 the model. In detail, except for calibration model for chroma, the coefficient of determination (R^2)
372 was higher than 0.96 for all the aforementioned quality parameters. Thus, for the test set validation
373 with one quarter of the data (randomly selected) RMSEPs ranging from 0.03÷0.04 for a_w , 0.04÷0.05
374 for moisture content and 4.54÷4.99 for SSC were obtained. The latter performance parameter was
375 comparable with both calibration and cross-validation results. Moreover, the model obtained from
376 feature selection (i.e. iPLS model) usually allowed the use of a lower number of latent variables in
377 comparison with full-spectrum model (i.e. PLS model).

378 The model for chroma determination resulted in lower R^2 but still in good performance. In
379 fact, although the correlation was smaller (R^2 from 0.77 to 0.86), the model performance was
380 acceptable, showing a RMSEP ranging from 2.31 to 2.75. Considering that the 1100-2300-nm
381 spectral band is not directly related to colour information, results obtained by the indirect
382 measurement of changes in chroma can be considered very good. However, it can be speculated that
383 by including the visible range the model performance could be improved considerably.

384 Generally, with respect to the treatment, iPLS algorithm led to a higher number of selected
385 features for microwave-heated samples, which also differed from the control treatment in terms of
386 selected wavelengths. Results suggest that effect of microwave heating on water loss and changes in
387 microstructure was pronounced, affecting the model development.

388 Table 3 also gives an overview of the spectral pre-treatments effectively used in the selected
389 models. In general, reducing and/or removing uninformative variance from the raw spectral data

390 was essential for the development of well-performing regression models as all best models use
391 spectral pre-treatments. In fact, it can be inferred that SNV scatter correction was necessary to
392 minimize the RMSE and thus to obtain the highest R^2 . This may either mean that the variation in
393 light scattering negatively interfered with spectral information related to chemical and
394 physicochemical parameters. Savitzky-Golay smoothing filter improved the prediction performance
395 for all regression challenges. Thus, the need for a smoothing filter suggests that spectral data were
396 slightly affected by issues due to noise and other irrelevant information. Mean centering was
397 effective in improving regression performance through spectral resolution enhancement; in fact, this
398 technique led to superior results as compared to those obtained from non-mean-centered spectra.

399

400 *3.4 Classification models*

401 In Table 4 are summarized the combinations of spectral pre-treatments, discriminant
402 algorithms and features which gave the best classification performance for the assignment of each
403 apple wedge to a specific drying phase on the basis of its spectral profile. The optimal combination
404 of spectral pre-processing was similar of those already selected for the development regression
405 models. Thus, in this case also, pre-treatment methods such as SNV (for baseline correction),
406 Savitzky-Golay smoothing filter (for noise reduction) and Mean Centering (for resolution
407 enhancement) were selected as best combination for removing/reducing unwanted background
408 information (i.e. light scattering and noise arising from various physical and/or chemical processes).

409 Considering the large variability observed in samples during drying, models show very high
410 classification performances. In fact, all the models possessed very-good (> 0.90) or excellent ($>$
411 0.95) sensitivity and specificity rates for all drying phases (i.e. ‘Drying Phase I’, ‘Drying Phase II’
412 and ‘Drying Phase III’). This means that the models had a greater ability to discriminate between
413 the classes with respect to another class. In particular, all models had the highest sensitivity rate and
414 specificity rate for ‘Drying Phase I’ and ‘Drying Phase III’. This indicates that the classification of
415 apple wedges as belonging or not belonging to both initial and final drying phases was the most

416 accurate. Moreover, it should be noted that the worst predictive ability was always paired to
417 ‘Drying Phase II’. This can probably be explained by the fact that ‘Drying phase II’ showed (1) a
418 lower within-class similarity and (2) a higher between-class similarity than both ‘Drying Phase I’ or
419 ‘Drying Phase III’.

420 Feature selection demonstrated that development of a drying-phase recognition model based
421 on few wavelengths is feasible. In particular, models obtained from a reduced number of features
422 (i.e. iPLS-DA) showed discriminant performances very similar to models computed from the full
423 spectrum (i.e. PLS-DA). Moreover, iPLS-DA models were always characterized by a higher
424 variance explained by a lower number of latent variables. This is confirmed by both Fig. 5a and 5b,
425 which show an example of tight pattern similarity between scores from PLS-DA and iPLS-DA
426 models. Finally, yet importantly, the experimentation showed a negligible effect of microwave
427 heating treatment on the performances of both PLS-DA and iPLS-DA models. However, feature
428 selection seems to be affected by the thermal treatment as selected wavelengths were totally
429 different between treatments. Thus, prior to implementation in industry this approach should be
430 further validated on a larger sample size covering the most important variations expected from
431 structural changes in apples due to the effect of both thermal treatment and drying process.

432

433 **4.0 CONCLUSIONS**

434 In this study, the potential of near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy in the 1100-2300-nm spectral
435 range has been evaluated to proactively and non-destructively detect and monitor changes in quality
436 parameters (i.e. water activity, moisture content, SSC and colour) of apple wedges (*Malus*
437 *domestica* B. var. Gala) during hot-air drying. For this purpose, both PLS regression and PLS-DA
438 classification models were developed. Optimal features were selected by using the interval PLS
439 (iPLS) and the interval PLS-DA (iPLS-DA) algorithms both configured in stepwise forward mode.
440 The impact of the microwave heating (at 850 W for 45 sec) as enzyme inactivator on model
441 performance was also investigated.

442 In general, both PLS and PLS-DA models obtained either very good or excellent results.
443 Specifically for regression analysis, models characterized by remarkable performances were
444 obtained for water activity ($R^2 = 0.97\div 0.98$; RMSEP = 0.03 \div 0.04), moisture content ($R^2 =$
445 $0.97\div 0.98$; RMSEP = 0.04 \div 0.05), SSC ($R^2 = 0.96\div 0.97$; RMSEP = 4.54 \div 4.99) and chroma ($R^2 =$
446 $0.77\div 0.86$; RMSEP = 2.31 \div 2.75). Regarding the discriminant analysis, PLS-DA algorithms
447 obtained high accuracy rate in classifying the apple wedges into classes as drying phases based on
448 the spectral profile. Specifically, NIR spectroscopy showed an excellent classification (accuracy
449 rate > 0.95) for apple wedges belonging to ‘Drying phase I’ and ‘Drying phase II’. Differently,
450 misclassified apple wedges were primarily assigned to ‘Drying phase II’, which however showed a
451 very-good accuracy rate higher than 0.90. It should be noted that the development of regression and
452 classification models were affected by the microwave heating treatment in terms of number of
453 features and selected wavelengths. Consequently, the proposed method should be further validated
454 to circumvent model robustness issues due to both water loss and microstructural changes in apples
455 as consequence of thermal treatments.

456 Finally, the approach proposed in this research lays the foundations for an accurate smart-
457 drying system based on NIR spectroscopy in terms of regression and classification performances,
458 non-destructive analysis and automation. However, the number of wavelengths required in an
459 online drying device would be conditional of the spectral pre-treatment used. Future research should
460 include testing wavelengths not measured by the spectrophotometer used for this study, increasing
461 the light-beam intensity, and/or combining other chemometric methods, as these could improve the
462 performance and the robustness of the smart-drying system.

463

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471 **REFERENCES**

- 472 Aghbashlo, M., Hosseinpour, S., Mujumdar, A.S., 2015. Application of Artificial Neural Networks
473 (ANNs) in Drying Technology: A Comprehensive Review. *Dry. Technol.* 33, 1397–1462.
- 474 Akpinar, E.K., Bicer, Y., Yildiz, C., 2003. Thin layer drying of red pepper. *J. Food Eng.* 59, 99–
475 104.
- 476 Ambrose, A., Lohumi, S., Lee, W.H., Cho, B.K., 2016. Comparative nondestructive measurement
477 of corn seed viability using Fourier transform near-infrared (FT-NIR) and Raman
478 spectroscopy. *Sensors Actuators, B Chem.* 224, 500–506.
- 479 Awad, T.S., Moharram, H.A., Shaltout, O.E., Asker, D., Youssef, M.M., 2012. Applications of
480 ultrasound in analysis, processing and quality control of food: A review. *Food Res. Int.* 48,
481 410–427.
- 482 Awuah, G.B., Ramaswamy, H.S., Economides, A., 2007. Thermal processing and quality:
483 Principles and overview. *Chem. Eng. Process. Process Intensif.* 46, 584–602.
- 484 Benlloch-Tinoco, M., Igual, M., Rodrigo, D., Martínez-Navarrete, N., 2013. Comparison of
485 microwaves and conventional thermal treatment on enzymes activity and antioxidant capacity
486 of kiwifruit puree. *Innov. Food Sci. Emerg. Technol.* 19, 166–172.
- 487 Boysworth, M.K., Booksh, K.S., 2008. Aspects of multivariate calibration applied to near-infrared
488 spectroscopy, in: Burns, D.A., Ciurczak, E.W. (Eds.), *Handbook of Near-Infrared Analysis*.
489 CRC Press, New York, USA, pp. 207–229.
- 490 Brosnan, T., Sun, D.W., 2004. Improving quality inspection of food products by computer vision -
491 A review. *J. Food Eng.* 61, 3–16.
- 492 Chen, Q., Zhang, C., Zhao, J., Ouyang, Q., 2013. Recent advances in emerging imaging techniques
493 for non-destructive detection of food quality and safety. *TrAC - Trends Anal. Chem.* 52, 261–
494 274.
- 495 Chong, C.H., Figiel, A., Law, C.L., Wojdyło, A., 2014. Combined Drying of Apple Cubes by Using
496 of Heat Pump, Vacuum-Microwave, and Intermittent Techniques. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 7,

497 975–989.

498 Clarka, C.J., Hockings, P.D., Joyce, D.C., Mazucco, R.A., 1997. Application of magnetic resonance
499 imaging to pre- and post-harvest studies of fruits and vegetables. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.*
500 11, 1–21.

501 CRAN, 2016. Comprehensive R Archive Network. URL <http://cran.r-project.org>.

502 de Jong, S., 1993. SIMPLS: An alternative approach to partial least squares regression. *Chemom.*
503 *Intell. Lab. Syst.* 18, 251–263.

504 Dejaegher, B., Dhooghe, L., Goodarzi, M., Apers, S., Pieters, L., Vander Heyden, Y., 2011.
505 Classification models for neocryptolepine derivatives as inhibitors of the β -haematin
506 formation. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 705, 98–110.

507 Demirhan, E., Özbek, B., 2009. Color Change Kinetics of Microwave-Dried Basil. *Dry. Technol.*
508 27, 156–166.

509 Dénes, L., Zsom-Muha, V., Baranyai, L., Felföldi, J., 2012. Modelling of apple slice moisture
510 content by optical methods. *Acta Aliment.* 41, 39–51.

511 ElMasry, G., Sun, D.-W., 2010. Hyperspectral imaging for food quality analysis and control, in:
512 Sun, D.-W. (Ed.), *Hyperspectral Imaging for Food Quality Analysis and Control*. Academic
513 Press, London, UK, pp. 3–43.

514 Fernández, L., Castellero, C., Aguilera, J.M., 2005. An application of image analysis to dehydration
515 of apple discs. *J. Food Eng.* 67, 185–193.

516 Ghasemi-Varnamkhasti, M., Mohtasebi, S.S., Siadat, M., 2010. Biomimetic-based odor and taste
517 sensing systems to food quality and safety characterization: An overview on basic principles
518 and recent achievements. *J. Food Eng.* 100, 377–387.

519 Gomez, K.A., Gomez, A., 1984. *Statistical procedures for Agricultural Research*, second ed. ed.
520 John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, NY, USA.

521 Goodarzi, M., Heyden, Y. Vander, Funar-Timofei, S., 2013. Towards better understanding of
522 feature-selection or reduction techniques for Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship

523 models. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 42, 49–63.

524 Grabowski, S., Marcotte, M., Ramaswamy, H.S., 2003. Drying of fruits, vegetables and spices, in:
525 Chakraverty, A., Mujumdar, A.S., Vijaia Raghavan, G.S., Ramaswamy, H.S. (Eds.),
526 Handbook of Postharvest Technology: Cereals, Fruits, Vegetables, Tea, and Spices. Marcel
527 Dekker, Inc, New York, NY, USA, pp. 653–695.

528 Horwitz, W., 2005. Official methods of analysis of AOAC international, 18th Edition.

529 Jha, S.N., Narsaiah, K., Basediya, A.L., Sharma, R., Jaiswal, P., Kumar, R., Bhardwaj, R., 2011.
530 Measurement techniques and application of electrical properties for nondestructive quality
531 evaluation of foods-a review. *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 48, 387–411.

532 Kermasha, S., Bisakowski, B., Ramaswamy, H., Van de Voort, F.R., 1993. Thermal and Microwave
533 Inactivation of Soybean Lipoxygenase. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* 26, 215–219.

534 Krokida, M.K., Maroulis, Z.B., Saravacos, G.D., 2001. The effect of the method of drying on the
535 colour of dehydrated products. *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* 36, 53–59.

536 Krokida, M.K., Tsami, E., Maroulis, Z.B., 1998. Kinetics on Color Changes During Drying of
537 Some Fruits and Vegetables. *Dry. Technol.* 16, 667–685.

538 Latorre, M.E., Bonelli, P.R., Rojas, A.M., Gerschenson, L.N., 2012. Microwave inactivation of red
539 beet (*Beta vulgaris* L. var. *conditiva*) peroxidase and polyphenoloxidase and the effect of
540 radiation on vegetable tissue quality. *J. Food Eng.* 109, 676–684.

541 Lavelli, V., Kerr, W., 2012. Apple pomace is a good matrix for phytochemical retention. *J. Agric.*
542 *Food Chem.* 60, 5660–5666.

543 Liu, C., Liu, W., Lu, X., Chen, W., Yang, J., Zheng, L., 2016. Potential of multispectral imaging for
544 real-time determination of colour change and moisture distribution in carrot slices during hot
545 air dehydration, *Food Chemistry*. Elsevier Ltd.

546 Massantini, R., Moscetti, R., Monarca, D., Cecchini, M., Contini, M., Alfani, L.M., 2009. The
547 influence of cover crops and double harvest on storage of fresh hazelnuts (*Corylus Avellana*
548 L.). *Adv. Hortic. Sci.* 23, 231–237.

549 Matsui, K.N., Gut, J.A.W., de Oliveira, P.V., Tadini, C.C., 2008. Inactivation kinetics of
550 polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase in green coconut water by microwave processing. *J. Food*
551 *Eng.* 88, 169–176.

552 Mayor, L., Sereno, A.M., 2004. Modelling shrinkage during convective drying of food materials: A
553 review. *J. Food Eng.* 61, 373–386.

554 Montgomery, D.C., 2001. *Design and analysis of experiments*, Fifth edit. ed. Wiley & Sons, Inc.,
555 New York, USA.

556 Moscetti, R., Carletti, L., Monarca, D., Cecchini, M., Stella, E., Massantini, R., 2013a. Effect of
557 alternative postharvest control treatments on the storability of “Golden Delicious” apples. *J.*
558 *Sci. Food Agric.* 93, 2691–2697.

559 Moscetti, R., Frangipane, M.T., Monarca, D., Cecchini, M., Massantini, R., 2012. Maintaining the
560 quality of unripe, fresh hazelnuts through storage under modified atmospheres. *Postharvest*
561 *Biol. Technol.* 65, 33–38.

562 Moscetti, R., Haff, R.P., Aernouts, B., Saeys, W., Monarca, D., Cecchini, M., Massantini, R.,
563 2013b. Feasibility of Vis / NIR spectroscopy for detection of flaws in hazelnut kernels. *J. Food*
564 *Eng.* 1–7.

565 Moscetti, R., Saeys, W., Keresztes, J.C., Goodarzi, M., Cecchini, M., Danilo, M., Massantini, R.,
566 2015. Hazelnut Quality Sorting Using High Dynamic Range Short-Wave Infrared
567 Hyperspectral Imaging. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 8, 1593–1604.

568 Mujumdar, A.S., 2012. Editorial: The Role of Drying Technology in Sustainable R&D and
569 Innovation. *Dry. Technol.* 30.

570 Nadian, M.H., Rafiee, S., Aghbashlo, M., Hosseinpour, S., Mohtasebi, S.S., 2015. Continuous real-
571 time monitoring and neural network modeling of apple slices color changes during hot air
572 drying. *Food Bioprod. Process.* 94, 263–274.

573 Naes, T., Isaksson, T., Fearn, T., Davies, T., 2004. *A user-friendly guide to Multivariate Calibration*
574 *and Classification*. NIR publications, Chichester, UK.

- 575 Nicolai, B.M., Beullens, K., Bobelyn, E., Peirs, A., Saeys, W., Theron, K.I., Lammertyn, J., 2007.
576 Nondestructive measurement of fruit and vegetable quality by means of NIR spectroscopy: A
577 review. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.* 46, 99–118.
- 578 Olsen, C.M., Drake, C.L., Bunch, S.L., 1966. Some Biological Effects of Microwave Energy. *J.*
579 *Microw. Power* 1, 45–56.
- 580 Ozaki, Y., McClure, W.F., Christy, A.A. (Eds.), 2006. *Near-Infrared Spectroscopy in Food Science*
581 *and Technology*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, NJ, USA.
- 582 Rattanadecho, P., Makul, N., 2016. Microwave-Assisted Drying: A Review of the State-of-the-Art.
583 *Dry. Technol.* 34, 1–38.
- 584 Rodríguez, Ó., Santacatalina, J. V., Simal, S., Garcia-Perez, J. V., Femenia, A., Rosselló, C., 2014.
585 Influence of power ultrasound application on drying kinetics of apple and its antioxidant and
586 microstructural properties. *J. Food Eng.* 129, 21–29.
- 587 Romano, G., Nagle, M., Argyropoulos, D., Müller, J., 2011. Laser light backscattering to monitor
588 moisture content, soluble solid content and hardness of apple tissue during drying. *J. Food*
589 *Eng.* 104, 657–662.
- 590 Sacilik, K., Elicin, A.K., 2006. The thin layer drying characteristics of organic apple slices. *J. Food*
591 *Eng.* 73, 281–289.
- 592 Saeys, W., Velazco-Roa, M. a, Thennadil, S.N., Ramon, H., Nicolai, B.M., 2008. Optical properties
593 of apple skin and flesh in the wavelength range from 350 to 2200 nm. *Appl. Opt.* 47, 908–919.
- 594 Savitzky, A., Golay, M.J.E., 1964. Smoothing and Differentiation of Data by Simplified Least
595 Squares Procedures. *Anal. Chem.* 36, 1627–1639.
- 596 Su, Y., Zhang, M., Mujumdar, A.S., 2014. Recent Developments in Smart Drying Technology. *Dry.*
597 *Technol.* 33, 260–276.
- 598 Su, Y., Zhang, M., Mujumdar, A.S., 2015. Recent Developments in Smart Drying Technology. *Dry.*
599 *Technol.* 33, 260–276.
- 600 Vega-Gálvez, A., Ah-Hen, K., Chacana, M., Vergara, J., Martínez-Monzó, J., García-Segovia, P.,

601 Lemus-Mondaca, R., Di Scala, K., 2012. Effect of temperature and air velocity on drying
602 kinetics, antioxidant capacity, total phenolic content, colour, texture and microstructure of
603 apple (var. Granny Smith) slices. *Food Chem.* 132, 51–59.

604 Wise, B.M., 2009. Eigen vector research wiki - Using Cross-Validation. URL
605 <http://wiki.eigenvector.com>. Accessed 11.09.2015.

606 Xing, J., Guyer, D., Ariana, D., Lu, R., 2008. Determining optimal wavebands using genetic
607 algorithm for detection of internal insect infestation in tart cherry. *Sens. Instrum. Food Qual.*
608 *Saf.* 2, 161–167.

609 Yi, J., Zhou, L., Bi, J., Chen, Q., Liu, X., Wu, X., 2015. Impacts of Pre-Drying Methods on
610 Physicochemical Characteristics, Color, Texture, Volume Ratio, Microstructure and
611 Rehydration of Explosion Puffing Dried Pear Chips. *J. Food Process. Preserv.* n/a-n/a.

612 Zheng, H., Lu, H., 2011. Effect of microwave pretreatment on the kinetics of ascorbic acid
613 degradation and peroxidase inactivation in different parts of green asparagus (*Asparagus*
614 *officinalis* L.) during water blanching. *Food Chem.* 128, 1087–1093.

615

FIGURE CAPTIONS

- Figure 1.** *Flowchart of the development of classification model for drying phases detection using K-means clustering (unsupervised learning) paired to PLS-DA algorithm (supervised learning). (*) Unlabelled data corresponds to changes in water activity, moisture, color and soluble solids content values collected during 8-h drying. (**) NIR labelled data corresponds to spectral data (X) acquired during 8-h drying and paired to class membership (i.e. response variable, Y) becoming from K-means.*
- Figure 2.** *First-order kinetics of the residual peroxidase activity for control (a) and microwaves (b) treatments. D-value states for decimal reduction time, which is the treatment time required to reduce the residual POD activity to at least 0.1.*
- Figure 3.** *Mean relative absorbance spectra for control (a) and microwave heating (b) treatments at different drying times (i.e. from 0- to 8-h drying with step of 1-h drying).*
- Figure 4.** *PLS regression plots of Y-measured (reference) and Y-predicted (NIR) values for water activity (column a), moisture (column b), chroma (column c) soluble solids content (column d) monitored during 8-h drying in both control (row 1) and microwave (row 2) treated apples. PLS regression plots refer to models based obtained from the full spectrum.*
- Figure 5.** *Drying phases' spatial distribution plots obtained from PLS-DA (a) and iPLS-DA (b) models for '0-2 h', '3-4 h' and '5-8 h' classes (i.e. drying phases) of the control treatment. Percentages of the explained variance are reported in parentheses on the axes. Green point with red outline corresponds to 'Drying Phase II' sample misclassified as 'Drying Phase I'. Red point with green outline corresponds to 'Drying Phase I' sample misclassified as 'Drying Phase II'. Blue point with green outline corresponds to 'Drying Phase III' sample misclassified as 'Drying Phase II'. Green point with blue outline corresponds to 'Drying Phase II' sample misclassified as 'Drying Phase III'.*

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

TABLE CAPTIONS

- Table 1.** *Experimental design for both hot-water and microwave blanching treatments. HW – hot-water blanching; MW – microwave heating.*
- Table 2.** *Main effect of drying time on the chemical and physicochemical quality parameters of apple wedges. Mean values with no common letters are statistically different according to HSD ($p \leq 0.05$). Drying times were clustered in drying phases (i.e. I, II and III) according to the results obtained from the K-means cluster analysis.*
- Table 3.** *Summary of performance metrics for the combinations of treatment, spectral pre-processing and regression algorithm (i.e. PLS and iPLS) complexity which gave the best results during 8-h drying.*
- Table 4.** *Summary of performance metrics for the combinations of treatment, spectral pre-processing and classification algorithm (i.e. PLS-DA and iPLS-DA) complexity which gave the best results during 8-h drying.*

TABLE 1

Hot-water blanching			Microwave heating		
ID	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	ID	Power (W)	Time (min)
HW-80-0	80	0.0	MW-350-0	350	0.00
HW-80-1	80	1.5	MW-350-1	350	0.25
HW-80-2	80	3.0	MW-350-2	350	0.55
HW-80-3	80	5.0	MW-350-3	350	0.75
HW-80-4	80	10.0	MW-350-4	350	1.00
HW-90-0	90	0.0	MW-650-0	650	0.00
HW-90-1	90	1.5	MW-650-1	650	0.25
HW-90-2	90	3.0	MW-650-2	650	0.50
HW-90-3	90	5.0	MW-650-3	650	0.75
HW-95-0	95	0.0	MW-650-4	650	1.00
HW-95-1	95	0.5	MW-850-0	850	0.00
HW-95-2	95	1.0	MW-850-1	850	0.25
HW-95-3	95	1.5	MW-850-2	850	0.50
HW-95-4	95	3.0	MW-850-3	850	0.75
			MW-850-4	850	1.00

Table 2

TABLE 2

Treatment	Drying phase (K-means)	Drying time (hour)	Water activity (a _w)	Moisture (relative)	SSC (°Brix)	Lightness (L*)	Redness (a*)	Yellowness (b*)	Hue angle (h)	Chroma (C*)
Control	I	0	0.88 ± 0.04 a	0.89 ± 0.00 a	11.39 ± 1.43 e	71.66 ± 1.65 d	2.92 ± 0.96 c	23.30 ± 1.83 g	82.93 ± 1.97 a	23.49 ± 1.89 f
		1	0.84 ± 0.04 ab	0.85 ± 0.02 a	13.01 ± 0.35 e	71.23 ± 2.53 de	5.01 ± 0.73 b	28.71 ± 1.33 f	80.13 ± 1.02 bc	29.14 ± 1.42 e
		2	0.82 ± 0.05 b	0.83 ± 0.03 a	14.74 ± 0.52 e	68.89 ± 1.56 d	6.06 ± 0.80 b	31.59 ± 1.76 e	79.17 ± 0.99 bcd	32.17 ± 1.85 d
	II	3	0.64 ± 0.03 c	0.58 ± 0.09 b	24.85 ± 1.96 d	75.20 ± 2.38 bc	8.16 ± 1.24 a	37.67 ± 2.76 bcd	77.79 ± 1.44 de	38.56 ± 2.86 bc
		4	0.62 ± 0.03 c	0.50 ± 0.09 c	35.77 ± 4.40 c	76.65 ± 1.84 ab	6.17 ± 1.05 b	36.07 ± 2.55 d	80.34 ± 1.23 bc	36.60 ± 2.65 c
	III	5	0.45 ± 0.03 d	0.16 ± 0.06 e	38.85 ± 2.29 c	78.46 ± 2.69 ab	6.46 ± 2.00 b	39.28 ± 2.44 abc	80.75 ± 2.35 b	39.84 ± 2.67 ab
		6	0.46 ± 0.04 d	0.25 ± 0.11 d	58.50 ± 4.93 b	76.22 ± 2.85 ab	8.34 ± 2.03 a	40.48 ± 2.49 a	78.43 ± 2.50 cde	41.37 ± 2.67 ab
		7	0.45 ± 0.04 d	0.10 ± 0.04 ef	69.11 ± 5.42 a	73.13 ± 1.89 cd	8.89 ± 1.19 a	37.49 ± 2.65 cd	76.63 ± 1.73 e	38.55 ± 2.65 bc
		8	0.42 ± 0.02 d	0.10 ± 0.04 f	75.48 ± 2.64 a	73.25 ± 3.27 cd	9.03 ± 1.76 a	40.07 ± 1.67 ab	77.33 ± 2.30 de	41.11 ± 1.78 ab
		<i>p</i> value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	<i>HSD</i>	0.04	0.06	7.59	2.72	1.60	2.56	2.09	2.68	
Microwave heating	I	0	0.91 ± 0.03 a	0.87 ± 0.02 a	11.97 ± 1.15 d	44.21 ± 2.59 abc	-2.07 ± 0.45 c	13.61 ± 2.25 d	98.70 ± 1.46 ab	13.77 ± 2.27 d
		1	0.92 ± 0.02 a	0.83 ± 0.02 ab	15.20 ± 1.21 d	42.05 ± 1.46 bcd	-2.03 ± 0.75 c	13.19 ± 2.54 d	99.35 ± 4.40 a	13.38 ± 2.45 d
		2	0.88 ± 0.04 a	0.81 ± 0.02 b	16.84 ± 3.36 d	45.46 ± 1.86 ab	-1.48 ± 0.59 c	16.32 ± 2.54 cd	95.31 ± 2.14 bc	16.40 ± 2.53 cd
	II	3	0.75 ± 0.07 b	0.62 ± 0.04 c	34.25 ± 11.43 c	46.44 ± 1.16 a	-1.52 ± 0.70 c	19.28 ± 2.22 c	94.72 ± 2.34 c	19.35 ± 2.18 c
		4	0.60 ± 0.12 c	0.42 ± 0.09 d	46.75 ± 9.74 b	43.29 ± 3.98 abcd	0.54 ± 1.86 b	25.08 ± 3.95 ab	89.17 ± 3.92 d	25.14 ± 4.00 ab
	III	5	0.58 ± 0.11 c	0.36 ± 0.06 e	48.63 ± 12.31 b	44.44 ± 3.84 ab	1.23 ± 1.90 b	27.23 ± 3.56 a	87.80 ± 3.63 d	27.31 ± 3.64 a
		6	0.36 ± 0.02 d	0.19 ± 0.01 f	73.21 ± 13.23 a	40.46 ± 1.70 d	0.98 ± 0.90 b	24.64 ± 2.85 ab	87.87 ± 2.00 d	24.68 ± 2.87 ab
		7	0.35 ± 0.02 d	0.18 ± 0.02 f	63.49 ± 6.14 a	40.85 ± 2.83 cd	0.79 ± 2.03 b	22.95 ± 2.37 b	88.28 ± 4.64 d	23.04 ± 2.45 b
		8	0.32 ± 0.02 d	0.19 ± 0.03 f	73.22 ± 3.80 a	43.49 ± 7.86 abcd	3.87 ± 3.32 a	25.75 ± 6.21 ab	82.19 ± 5.37 e	26.15 ± 6.58 ab
		<i>p</i> value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
	<i>HSD</i>	0.08	0.04	10.73	3.58	1.64	3.37	3.54	3.46	

TABLE 3

Treatment	Parameter	Algorithm	Number of features	Wavelengths (nm)	Spectral pre-treatment			LVs ⁱ	RMSE ^l		Bias		R ²	
					SG ^e	SC ^f	MC ^g		C ^m	P ⁿ	C	P	C	P
Control	a _w ^a	PLS ^c	601	1100-2300	5	SNV ^h	Yes	4	0.03	0.03	2.2E-16	-5.7E-05	0.98	0.97
		iPLS ^d	6	1144, 1496, 1876, 2118, 2166, 2290				4	0.02	0.03	-3.5E-16	9.1E-05	0.98	0.98
	Moisture	PLS	601	1100-2300	5	SNV	Yes	5	0.04	0.04	1.1E-16	-4.2E-04	0.98	0.98
		iPLS	2	1330, 1878				2	0.04	0.04	-3.1E-16	-1.3E-04	0.98	0.98
	SSC ^b	PLS	601	1100-2300	9	SNV	Yes	5	4.48	4.86	0.00E+00	6.07E-03	0.97	0.96
		iPLS	2	1310, 1878				2	4.61	4.63	4.49E-14	1.09E-02	0.97	0.97
	Chroma (C*)	PLS	601	1100-2300	15	SNV	Yes	6	2.23	2.43	-7.1E-15	-1.5E-02	0.87	0.85
		iPLS	4	1156, 1630, 2180, 2244				4	2.25	2.33	1.8E-14	-1.3E-02	0.87	0.86
Microwave heating	a _w	PLS	601	1100-2300	9	SNV	Yes	6	0.04	0.04	0.0E+00	-7.2E-05	0.98	0.97
		iPLS	8	1340, 1444, 1534, 1652, 1658, 1768, 1868, 1888				4	0.04	0.04	5.4E-17	3.0E-04	0.98	0.97
	Moisture	PLS	601	1100-2300	7	SNV	Yes	8	0.04	0.05	-1.1E-16	-1.4E-03	0.98	0.97
		iPLS	7	1140, 1354, 1424, 1438, 1876, 1892, 2108				5	0.04	0.04	4.4E-16	-3.4E-05	0.98	0.98
	SSC	PLS	601	1100-2300	9	SNV	Yes	3	4.73	5.01	0.0E+00	-2.6E-02	0.96	0.96
		iPLS	3	1152, 1336, 1890				2	4.48	4.59	-1.0E-14	8.5E-04	0.96	0.96
	Chroma (C*)	PLS	601	1100-2300	5	SNV	Yes	4	2.58	2.77	-7.1E-15	-7.3E-03	0.80	0.77
		iPLS	5	1162, 1272, 1518, 2128, 2182				5	2.40	2.48	3.0E-15	-9.2E-03	0.82	0.81

^a Water activity, ^b Soluble Solids Content, ^c Partial Least Squares regression, ^d Interval Partial Least Squares regression, ^e Savitzky-Golay filter window, ^f Scatter correction algorithm, ^g Standard Normal Variate, ^h Mean Centering, ⁱ Latent Variables, ^l Root Mean Squared Error, ^m Calibration, ⁿ Prediction.

TABLE 4

Treatment	Algorithm	Number of features	Wavelengths (nm)	Spectral pre-treatment			LVs ^g	Drying phase (K-means)	Drying period (hours)	Sensitivity		Specificity		Accuracy	
				SG ^c	SC ^d	MC ^f				C ^h	P ⁱ	C	P	C	P
Control	PLS-DA ^a	601	1100-2300	9	SNV ^e	Yes	3	I	0-2	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.99
								II	3-4	0.96	0.96	0.92	0.92	0.94	0.94
								III	5-8	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.98
	iPLS-DA ^b	4	1548, 1852, 2146, 2184	9	SNV	Yes	2	I	0-2	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.99
								II	3-4	0.96	0.96	0.93	0.93	0.95	0.95
								III	5-8	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Microwave heating	PLS-DA	601	1100-2300	9	SNV	Yes	6	I	0-3	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.98
								II	4-5	0.95	0.92	0.87	0.87	0.91	0.89
								III	6-8	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.96	0.97	0.96
	iPLS-DA	4	1126, 1154, 1620, 2192	9	SNV	Yes	3	I	0-3	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.98
								II	4-5	0.96	0.96	0.85	0.84	0.91	0.90
								III	6-8	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98

^a Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis, ^b Interval Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis, ^c Savitzky-Golay filter window, ^d Scatter correction, ^e Standard Normal Variate, ^f Mean Centering, ^g Latent Variables, ^h Calibration, ⁱ Prediction.

Figure 3a - interactive

[Click here to download Supplementary Interactive Plot Data \(CSV\): Figure 3a - interactive.csv](#)

Figure 3b - interactive

[Click here to download Supplementary Interactive Plot Data \(CSV\): Figure 3b - interactive.csv](#)